

Swin Transformer Applied to Breast MRI Super-Resolution in a Cross-Cohort Dataset

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Abstract—Advancements in the care for patients with breast cancer have demanded the development of biomechanical breast models for the planning and risk mitigation of such invasive surgical procedures. However, these approaches require large amounts of high-quality magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) training data that is of difficult acquisition and availability. Although this can be solved using synthetic data, generating high resolution images comes at the price of very high computational constraints and typically low performances. On the other hand, producing lower resolution samples yields better results and efficiency but falls short of meeting health professional standards. Therefore, this work aims to validate a joint approach between lower resolution generative models and the proposed super-resolution architecture, titled Shifted Window Image Restoration (SWinIR), which was used to achieve a 4x increase in image size of breast cancer patient MRI samples. Results prove to be promising and to further expand upon the super-resolution state-of-the-art, achieving good maximum peak signal-to-noise ratio of 41.36 and structural similarity index values of 0.962 and thus beating traditional methods and other machine learning architectures.

Index Terms—breast cancer, super-resolution, machine learning, medical image analysis, synthetic image generation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Despite lower death rates amongst patients, breast cancer incidence has risen in the past four decades [1]. Resection through lumpectomy is a viable surgical option [2] for which biomechanical models have been used as a visualisation aid in the past [3]. However, their fidelity has been pointed out as a challenge [4], mostly due to the scarce amounts of available data. In some studies, only a very small number of patients were used [5], which can compromise the use of those models in real applications. This becomes a more pressing issue when using machine learning models such as in [6].

The goal behind biomechanical algorithms is to understand the interactions between forces / external stimuli and living tissue, namely the deformation of breast during patient movement and position changes, which may lead clinicians to fault in their invasive procedures due to visualisation misguidance. The interdependency of the multiple slices of an exam further increases the complexity of modelling such interactions.

The acquisition and usage of data in the medical field, however, is not as easy due to privacy regulations, such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act, HIPPA, in the USA and the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR, in the European Union. As a result, efforts have been made to generate synthetic data [7], [8], although the generation of highly complex and clinically-sized MRI samples remains a challenge in the field. Thus, by lowering the resolution of artificial samples and said biomechanical models’ inputs we aim to trade-off image quality for training and

inference speed, while maintaining spatially consistent slices and dividing the burden of realistic high-quality breast MRI sample generation in two: low-resolution generation combined with super-resolution techniques for clinical viability.

This study proposes super resolution techniques for synthetic low quality breast cancer images. In other words, the developed pipeline aims to produce a machine learning architecture with which to increase the size of 2D breast cancer patient MRI slices. These enhanced samples are to be fed to the mentioned biomechanical models, seeing as they now are up to the medical standard of quality and can also be assessed by health professionals. The project also emphasises the need for this model to be able to comprehend and take into account the characteristics which distinguish real MRI samples from synthetic ones, namely artifacts and excessive blurring, and to be able to deal with these issues in the best way possible. Seeing as the aim of the project is to also lessen the computational burden of the whole generative process, efficiency is of high importance and should also be optimised.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Medical Imaging Data Enhancement

Single image super-resolution (SISR) is a technique associated to the betterment of an image's quality, usually by increasing the original size [9]. The purpose, therefore, is to produce a high-resolution (HR) version of the input low-resolution (LR) image sample by filling in the resolution gap and inferring on what the structural missing data is based on the surrounding LR components. Traditionally, this role was assigned to analytical computer vision algorithms, such as bicubic interpolation [10], but advances in deep learning and the need for HR images in clinical assessment have lead to the training of more complex models such as Convolutional Neural Networks [11] (CNNs) and Generative Adversarial Networks [12] (GANs). These proposed methods have further elevated the field's state-of-the-art by leveraging their convolutional frameworks in order to capture hierarchical and contextual features, thus enabling the generation of HR images with improved perceptual quality.

As it stands now, the state-of-the-art indicates that there is no clear gold standard for image super-resolution (SR) and that performance will vary depending on application. The intrinsic properties and characteristics of the different medical imaging modalities further emphasise the challenge of acquiring a one-size-fits-all solution to the problem. In this field, GANs have proven to be a valuable asset to use, as displayed by Mansoor et al. [13] and You et al. [14]. By introducing regularisation and data augmentation techniques, the proposed methods establish a robust and stable training process for the super-resolution of medical imaging modalities, including MRIs and Computed Tomographies (CTs). One other notable work in this field was that of Wang et al. [15], titled **Real Enhanced Super-Resolution GAN (Real-ESRGAN)**, which extended upon the developments by Ledig et al. [12] and Wang et al. [16] by introducing a perceptual discriminator module for the comparison of synthetic against real images.

B. Transformers in Super-Resolution

One of the first architectures to surpass CNNs in the field of SISR were Transformers. Originally designed for natural language processing, their self-attention mechanism excels at the capturing of long range data dependencies, something which is both valuable in SR [17] and that a static convolutional filter struggles to do [18], [19]. This has also been applied to medical imaging in the past, namely in the works of Forigua et al. [20] and Huang et al. [21].

The open-source deep learning architecture in which we have based this project, titled **Swin Transformer for Image Restoration (SwinIR)** was proposed by Liang et al. [22] and based on the original Shifted Window Transformer (Swin) by Liu et al. [23]. The latter was designed to be more computationally efficient than standard vision transformers by replacing convolution with local window self-attention. As such, SwinIR is composed of three main stages: shallow feature extraction, deep feature extraction (with multiple Residual Swin Transformer Blocks or RSTBs) and high-quality image reconstruction. By using a hierarchical feature representation and splitting the feature maps into non-overlapping windows, rather than computing attention across the whole sample, SwinIR has established itself as a low-cost model, which scales well even for high-resolution complex medical samples [24].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Description & Pre-Processing

For the scope of this project, we have used two separate datasets. The first dataset was collected at the Champalimaud Foundation (CF) and is composed of 72 MRI exams of 60 breast cancer patients ranging from 35 to 80 years old, each of which made up of 60 gray-scale axial image slices with a thickness of 3mm and acquired using the scanner Philips Ingenia 3.0T MRI. This private dataset was mostly used during the training stage. Lastly, the Duke's Breast Cancer MRI dataset [25], which features images from 922 patients with invasive breast cancer at multiple stages of development, spanning from 21 to 89 years old and both pre and post-menopause was also used. This data is composed of multiple dynamic contrast-enhanced (DCE)-MRIs, with an average of 60 slices per exam and was mostly used in validating the SR results. Both contain pre-operative T1-weighted MRI scans, of original 720×720 size. Despite the private dataset's smaller size, it was nevertheless employed during the training stage with the intent of approximating the final generated samples to those of the Champalimaud Foundation. It also reflects how the higher degree of processing and refinement of the Duke dataset contrasts with the private dataset's more realistic view of the detail and contents of the clinically used MRI volumes.

In the interest of uniformisation, both datasets were processed in the exact same manner. As for augmentation, the original HR versions were modified in 4 ways, thus expanding the dataset five-fold. These modifications were chosen from a comprehensive list proposed by Cossio [26] to introduce some degree of noise and blurring to the original samples:

- No Transformation ;
- Gaussian Noise adds random noise on all pixel from all channels, according to a normal distribution with mean 0 and a standard deviation of one-twentieth (1/20) of the standard deviation of the original image. Clipping is also applied, so as to limit values between 0 and 255 ;
- Box Blur takes a moving average of every pixel ;
- Gaussian Blur is a type of blur that applies a gaussian filter to the image, the amount of which can be controlled by adjusting the size of the gaussian kernel ;
- Simple Blur reduces the high-frequency components in an image, effectively smoothing it out ;

Fig. 1: Image pre-processing methods employed for data augmentation. All transformations are displayed in a zoomed in section of a low-resolution sample.

Lastly, each original HR image was downsized at a $4x$ scale, from 720×720 to 180×180 , this being the scale of SR attempted by the project. This resizing, using a Lanczos filter, meant that multiple LR training samples would be linked to the same original HR ground truth (GT) from which they originate, as Fig. 1 depicts. This pre-processing served as both data augmentation to bridge the small amount of samples in the private dataset and as a way to further push the model’s capability to adapt to the characteristics of synthetic and less refined imaging, such as artifacts and higher quantities of noise and blurring. As for data splitting, we have chosen to use a 60%-20%-20% split of the private dataset (training-validation-test) and leave the public Duke’s Breast Cancer entirely as a test phase-only resource for the reasons mentioned above.

B. Experimental Setup

As a method of achieving the proposed $4x$ super-resolution, this project has implemented and optimised the SwinIR architecture by resorting to both the Knowledge-Aware Image

TABLE I: Different model training configurations and hyperparameters. Empty parameters do not apply to the model’s architecture.

Hyperparameter	RSTB Layers	Window Size	Embedding Size	Learning Rate
Baseline	6	8	180	2E-04
Lightweight	4		60	
Real-ESRGAN		-		1E-04

Restoration (KAIR)ⁱ and SwinIRⁱⁱ repositories. In total, five different models were trained in order to assess the necessary training requirements that would provide the best performance, taking into account that SwinIR was not initially trained on medical imaging data.

Firstly, by training four versions of one of the model checkpoints provided by the original authorsⁱⁱⁱ, the work evaluated the impact of unfreezing some of its layers, or in other words partial fine-tuning (FT). This method entails the updating of only some chosen layers’ weight values, while the remaining architecture remains ‘frozen’. Therefore, it leverages the model’s innate capabilities and prior training with the optimisation of training efficiency as a method of finding a middle ground between performance and computational expense. This also allows us to understand the model’s ability to generalise and adapt to new samples and completely unseen imaging modalities with very distinct features from those it was trained on. Furthermore, results were recorded at different number of iterations, with the intent of not only increasing efficiency, but also predicting overfitting sensitivity.

Each of the four versions was obtained from the same model checkpoint and after unfreezing an increasing amount of layers starting from the final one. Seeing as we have designed four models, we will refer to *1*, *2* and *3 Layer Models* as the versions in which only the last one, two or three layers were unfrozen respectively, while *All Layers Model* indicates the updating of all layers and a full fine-tuned version (rather than partial like the previous three). Finally, one other model was trained from scratch, without access to pre-trained weights, and constructed using a more lightweight build settings. Both this lightweight and the fine-tuning checkpoint’s hyperparameter configuration are further detailed in table I. A summary of the data pre-processing and training pipeline can also be seen integrated in Fig. 2.

C. Performance Evaluation

Assessing super-resolution imaging model performance is a critical aspect to understanding the capabilities and limitation of deep learning in broaching the gap between human and machine understanding. As such, while **mean squared error (MSE)** is perfectly adequate for a back-propagating loss function, evaluation must also address more perceptual metrics. These try to mimic human perception and compare between samples at a more holistic and higher level which simple pixel-wise methods cannot correctly define. For the purpose of this work and in order to gauge the quality of artificial HR samples against their GT counterparts, we highlight the usage of:

ⁱ<https://github.com/cszn/KAIR>

ⁱⁱ<https://github.com/JingyunLiang/SwinIR>

ⁱⁱⁱ<https://github.com/JingyunLiang/SwinIR/releases/tag/v0.0>
001_classicalSR_DF2K_s64w8_SwinIR-M_x8.pth

Fig. 2: Developed approach for the data pre-processing and super-resolution training pipeline.

Structural Similarity index (SSIM) juxtaposes two samples by considering their luminance, contrast and structure. By analysing higher frequency details such as the texture and edges of the images, SSIM is also very sensitive to blurring and the loss of fine details, which are some of the aspects that super-resolution may have trouble modelling. The closer the value is to 1, the more similar the two provided images are ;

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is based on MSE and quantifies pixel-wise differences, so although is not as useful perceptually as SSIM, it can still be an asset when attempting to measure reconstruction quality. The higher the value, the more similar the images are and the less discrepancies ;

These metrics were computed for all trained SwinIR versions, as well as for the method of bicubic interpolation. These were also pitted against the previously mentioned pre-trained SwinIR checkpoint (with no FT) and a Real-ESRGAN model trained under the same conditions and data splits.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Because of the two distinct datasets we have included in the test phase, namely the public Duke’s Breast Cancer MRI dataset and the 20% split from the private dataset provided by Fundação Champalimaud, result analysis of the two was done separately. These results are displayed in table II and they allow for a number of conclusions to be made.

Regarding the private dataset section, partial fine-tuning seems to have very limited potential in altering the trajectory of results and even when more layers were unfrozen, this would only produce slight betterments. On the other hand, complete fine-tuning was the method to achieve the best results, making incredible strides compared to other experiments and leading one to believe that the architectural backbone and the layers which better transmit information about the training images

are indeed the first layers, due to having more direct access to the actual image space. Within this model, the fact that the best results were obtained at the earlier checkpoint of 100000 steps (PSNR of 35.95 and SSIM of 0.918) also suggests that complete fine-tuning may cause some degree of overfitting to the training dataset, which despite expanded, is still somewhat small. Moreover, seeing as a from scratch implementation did not achieve the same level of performance, even after quite a lot more iterations, this indicates that prior knowledge of real data can be valuable for the understanding and modelling of some breast anatomical structures and elements.

As for the public test dataset results, most of the phenomena mentioned in the previous paragraph are still present, with the all layers fine-tuning model being the best performer overall, achieving a PSNR of 41.36 and SSIM of 0.962. The fact that all PSNR and SSIM values are higher for this section of the table can be traced back to the public dataset’s increased homogeneity in both acquisition and pre-processing, making it of much easier understanding than the less refined training private dataset, which contains more artifacts and is closer to synthetic samples. This is further proven by comparing the two sections. Intuition would state that the best results would be those of the private test dataset, seeing as its source is the same as the data with which all models were trained. However, this is not the case, thus re-enforcing the idea that the private dataset may not be as generalisable, leading models to struggle with learning how to represent its image features accurately and consistently.

These conclusions are also very much reflected visually, as shown by analysis of figures 3 and 4. These samples prove that SwinIR HR results display a high degree of texture quality, contrast and brightness, very close to that of the original ground truth. On the other hand, bicubic interpolation, being the simplest method, appears to create a lot of blurring. Finally, Real-ESRGAN results suggest the occurrence of mode

Fig. 3: Qualitative results comprised of the results of each methodology (apart from Real-ESRGAN) for a zoomed-in portion of a 2D slice example from the private test set (also including the original HR and LR for comparison).

TABLE II: PSNR and SSIM value results for the proposed SwinIR models and all baseline methodologies according each of the two test datasets. * implies that all values of the number of iterations / training steps must be multiplied by 10^5 .

Method	Training Steps *	Dataset			
		Private / CF PSNR	SSIM	Public / Duke PSNR	SSIM
Bicubic Interpolation	-	32.47	0.856	37.60	0.941
Real-ESRGAN	4	31.01	0.820	31.82	0.847
SwinIR Checkpoint Baseline	-	33.61	0.874	39.45	0.954
SwinIR 1 Layer FT	1	34.75	0.895	40.78	0.956
	2	34.79	0.896	40.85	0.959
	3	34.76	0.895	40.81	0.958
	4	34.79	0.895	40.84	0.960
	5	34.78	0.895	40.88	0.959
SwinIR 2 Layers FT	1	34.78	0.895	40.89	0.959
	2	34.79	0.895	41.01	0.960
	3	34.75	0.894	41.00	0.960
	4	34.78	0.894	41.04	0.960
SwinIR 3 Layers FT	1	34.83	0.895	41.18	0.961
	2	34.81	0.894	41.22	0.961
	3	34.82	0.895	41.12	0.961
	4	34.80	0.894	41.20	0.962
	5	34.81	0.894	41.23	0.962
SwinIR All Layers FT	1	35.95	0.918	41.36	0.962
	2	34.92	0.895	41.27	0.962
	3	34.95	0.896	41.24	0.962
SwinIR Lightweight	1.2	34.46	0.900	39.15	0.934
	2.4	35.25	0.908	40.33	0.941
	3.6	35.49	0.913	40.57	0.953

collapse [27], perhaps due to data scarcity within the augmented private dataset, given the lower quality of all tissue textures and definition, as well as the major artifact numbers. Quantitative proximity between bicubic interpolation and the proposed methods also makes an argument for the unreliability of perceptual metrics when compared to human understanding, seeing as this traditional method’s results are always blurrier and less defined than their machine learning HR counterparts.

The original SwinIR model [22], having used the same evaluation metrics in $4x$ upscaling, has obtained a maximum PSNR of 32.92, and SSIM of 0.926; whereas the next best model, the Residual-in-Residual Dense Block (RRDB) [28], obtained a PSNR of 32.73 and SSIM of 0.920. In the work of Gu et al. [29], titled MedSRGAN+, a validation of the the developed models is performed for medical images. For MRI images, this architecture obtained a PSNR of 26.464 and

SSIM of 0.988. The medical imaging super-resolution model review by Umirzakova et al. [30] was also highly useful for the obtainal of comparison terms. For MRI images, the CFIPC achieved the best PSNR of the models analysed with a PSNR of 38.42 and SSIM of 0.910; and the TransMRSR scored the best SSIM, with a PSNR of 36.37 and a SSIM of 0.985. The SwinIR was also validated yielding a PSNR of 34.99 and SSIM of 0.855. In comparison, the best result obtained in this work showed a better PSNR than all other models and a SSIM only worse than the TransMRSR. It should be taken into account that these results offer limited insights, seeing as methodologies and training processes are extremely distinct and also because of the training dataset not being the same.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have researched the use of a Swin Transformer architecture as a means for high-quality 2D breast MRI super-resolution. Overall, the project proves not only to be a clear improvement over traditional and other deep learning techniques, but also both computationally efficient and tailored for the task at hand. In other words, it successfully achieves a better performance by fine-tuning SwinIR for synthetic-like MRI characteristics. A future expansion of the proposed work may include the use of actual synthetic samples in an unsupervised or few-shot manner, so as to mimic its properties more realistically. Additionally, by training biomechanical models with these results or having them be assessed by a specialist / radiologist, we could get further insight into what artifacts to correct and what other flaws may exist.

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Fig. 4: Qualitative results comprised of the results of each methodology for a 2D slice example from the private test set (also including the original HR and LR for comparison).

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